

Critical Infrastructure Protection in the Finance Sector

A 2030 Outlook

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1. Drivers of Critical Infrastructure Protection in the Finance Sector

For nearly fifteen years, the banking and finance sector has been undergoing a rapid digital transformation, which is propelled by advances in internet banking, mobile computing and mobile apps, payment technologies, and more recently machine learning and artificial intelligence. The deployment and use of these technologies is inevitably increasing the attack vector of financial services, while introducing new vulnerabilities for the critical infrastructures of the sector. Likewise, it creates new cybersecurity challenges, which add up to conventional physical security challenges of the sector like robberies against bank branches and Automatic Teller Machines (ATM). During the last decade, the world has witnessed a considerable number of notorious cyber-attacks against financial infrastructures [Satlas20], such as the 2016 attack against the SWIFT network of the Bangladesh Central Bank which results in loss of almost 81 million dollars' and it still considered one of the biggest cyber heists in history.

Back in 2021, the H2020 FISNEC project, a founding member of the ECSCI (European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures) cluster, studied some of the most prominent cyber-attacks against financial institutions and documented relevant cybersecurity challenges [Satlas20], [Soldatos19]. The latter included for example the need for information sharing and collaboration across financial organizations, the need for increased automation and intelligence in risk assessments, as well as the need for integrated critical infrastructure protection measures including cyber-physical threat intelligence. FINSEC has implemented and promoted solutions that aimed at remedying some of the above-listed challenges, yet such solutions have been deployed at scale.

Ever since, the context of the financial services and of the critical infrastructures of the financial sector has changed in directions that exacerbate existing risks. Ransomware attacks, social engineering attacks and phishing attempts are therefore on the rise, despite the sector's increased investments in cybersecurity and critical infrastructure protection. Moreover, the evolution of technology (e.g., Large Language Models and AI technologies) has introduced additional risks and enabled the launch of more sophisticated attacks than ever before. At the same time, there have been new regulatory developments such as the introduction of the Critical Entities Resilience (CER) in Europe. The critical infrastructures of the financial sector have been also severely influenced by the COVID19 pandemic outbreak (2020-2022) and the Russian-Ukrainian war (2022-today). Overall, the future of critical infrastructure protection (CIP) and critical infrastructure resilience (CIR) is driven by the following trends:

- **Unprecedented Digital Transformation:** The COVID19 pandemic has accelerated the digital transformation of financial organizations. During the pandemic there has been a surge of digital transactions and a reduction to the number of physical transactions. This trend is sustained

following the end of the pandemic. Furthermore, it is likely to be reinforced as banks are facing competition from FinTechs and technology companies that offer financial services and because of central bank's intention to modernize payment systems and offer digital currencies (e.g., ECB's Digital Euro¹).

- **Work from Home:** The COVID19 pandemic has also led to a significant rise to the number of banking employees that work from home. Following the end of the pandemic, banks and financial organizations are still offering hybrid work models and flexible working options to many thousands of the employees of the sector. This is coupled with trends like BYOD (Bring Your Own Device), which increase the potential vulnerabilities of the critical infrastructures that support the provision of financial services. Hence, it asks for strong cybersecurity than ever before.
- **Hybrid Financial Organizations:** Modern financial organizations are hybrid organizations providing both local and global services, while at the same time offering on-site and remote services to both customers and employees. This redefines critical infrastructure protection for the finance sector and strengthens need for cyber-physical threat intelligence.
- **New Security and Resilience requirements stemming from the Digital Finance package of the EU²:** The digital finance strategy of the EU specifies the need for secure management of various financial assets including for example crypto-assets, which has implications in security and resilience of the finance sector infrastructures that will support them. In this direction, there are already several legislative proposals concerning crypto-assets and digital resilience.
- **Regulatory Developments in the Financial Sector and Critical Entities:** Nowadays, the protection of critical infrastructures and critical entities of the financial sector must take place in the context of a new regulatory environment. This includes the latest regulatory developments in the financial sector such as the EU's 6 AML Directive (6 AMLD), which was implemented by regulated entities in June 2021 and strengthen anti-money laundering (AML) rules in the EU putting higher responsibility on regulated entities to fight financial crime. It also includes regulatory developments in the CIP space, such as the CER directive that aims to strengthen the resilience of essential entities and infrastructure across Europe based on a more robust framework for securing vital services and infrastructures.
- **The Interdependencies of Critical Infrastructures for Finance to Other Types of Critical Infrastructures:** In an increasingly interconnected world, critical infrastructures of different sectors become interconnected and interdependent in the scope of cross-sector value chains. Hence, any disruption on critical infrastructures of the finance sector is likely to affect the operation of other critical infrastructures in sectors like manufacturing, logistics, insurance, and healthcare. It is not accident that a SWIFT ban against some Russian banks was prioritized in the list of sanctions imposed by the EU and other western countries. Overall, CIP must consider the interdependencies of different infrastructures, as well as related cascading effects.
- **New Risk stemming from the emerging of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Generative AI:** The release of ChatGPT back in November 2022 has opened new horizons in enterprise productivity. Modern enterprises leverage LLMs and GenAI tools for a wide range of enterprise tasks in areas like marketing, product development, and data analysis. Nevertheless, LLMs has also created opportunities for launching cyber-attacks at a lower effort and cost than ever before. For instance, GenAI tools like FraudGPT and WormGPT empower hackers to tailor malicious codes and viruses using a few interactive chat-like commands. Therefore, there is need for developing cyber-defences against the emerging wave of GenAI powered attacks against critical entities of the finance sector.

¹ https://www.ecb.europa.eu/paym/digital_euro/html/index.en.html

² https://finance.ec.europa.eu/publications/digital-finance-package_en

In this security landscape, this whitepaper reviews the main challenges faced by financial organization when it comes to protecting their critical assets. Moreover, it proposes solutions that can effectively combat these challenges and provides recommendations for financial institutions and other stakeholders.

2. Challenges and Limitations

Some of the main challenges and limitation faced by financial organizations in the scope of their cyber-security and critical infrastructure protection efforts include:

- **Challenge 1 - Infrastructures Complexity:** Legacy financial organizations deploy and operate complex digital infrastructures, which include elements from both legacy (e.g., legacy databases and data warehouses) and emerging technologies (e.g., BigData infrastructures). This increases the potential risks and asks for protecting complex technology stacks that are likely to including various security gaps and vulnerabilities.
- **Challenge 2 - Third-Party Risks:** Large financial organizations (e.g., banks, regulators) collaborate with many different technology vendors and partners. This means that sensitive data and other critical cyber-assets are accessible to third parties. This weakens the security of the financial value chain, as security weaknesses at a third-party can affect assets of the critical infrastructure leading to data breaches, and other serious security incidents.
- **Challenge 3 - Limited Information Sharing and Collaboration:** Despite the importance of sharing information across different actors of the financial services value chain and the advent of relevant structures (e.g., Information Sharing and Analysis Centres (ISAC) for the finance sector), stakeholders are still reluctant to share information. This mainly due to the lack of trust across different actors and second thoughts about potential brand damage.
- **Challenge 4 - Fragmentation of Security Resources and Services:** Along with limited information sharing, there is also a fragmentation of security measures across the financial supply chain. In most cases security systems are “siloes” with poor interaction between each other, which increases the attack surface of the financial value chain.
- **Challenge 5- Blockchain and Crypto-Assets Security Challenges:** The rise of crypto-assets and blockchain projects has provided financial organizations with a host of opportunities for novel products and services. Nevertheless, these opportunities come with additional security challenges as many blockchain projects have been found to come with various security vulnerabilities.
- **Challenge 6 - Regulatory Compliance in a highly volatile environment:** Regulatory mandates in the financial sector ask for additional security measures that are aimed to protect consumer data, while at the same time increasing the resilience of financial services. The challenge is considerable also given the high volatility of the regulatory environment. In this context, ensuring and maintaining regulatory compliance requires significant effort and costs, while at the same demanding a continuous investment in order to keep up with the evolution of the regulatory environment.
- **Challenge 7 - Talent and Skills Gaps within Employees:** These is a proclaimed talent gap in security/cybersecurity among most financial sector professionals. This is a set back to the implementing effective resilience measure and to enforcing security policies. For instance, there are many cases where weak credentials are used.
- **Challenge 8 - Poor Customers' Awareness:** Apart from financial sector employees, there are also many security illiterate customers. In an era where finance sector infrastructures empower many customer facing transactions, this becomes a major security challenge.

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The above list of challenges is not exhaustive, yet representative of some key security risks that must be addressed by modern critical infrastructure operators.

3. Solution Guidelines: Towards new CIP Capabilities and Resilience

To address the above-listed challenges there is need for developing, adopting and deploying novel CIP solutions for the critical infrastructures of the finance sector. Specifically, the following solution guidelines are envisaged:

3.1. Technical and Technological Guidelines

- **Guideline 1 – Technical and Regulatory Solutions fostering Increased Collaboration across Value Chain Actors – Public Private partnerships:** The development of decentralized and trusted solutions for sharing information could boost the collaboration and data/information exchange across value chain participants (e.g., financial organizations, public sector organizations, other critical infrastructure providers). In this direction, decentralization technologies (e.g., blockchain) and federated data management technologies (e.g., financial data spaces for cybersecurity information) can be exploited. The design, implementation and use of such technological solutions must be driven by the regulatory environment. Hence, there is a need for regulatory prompts and incentives for sharing security information following existing examples and best practices of information sharing across banks (e.g., information sharing for KYC and AML purposes). Relevant recommendations for sharing information across financial institutions have been produced by The Financial Action Task Force (FATF), which can serve as a best practice example that can be extended/replicate to information for security and resilience purposes. Moreover, public private partnership that could boost the resilience of critical entities must be pursued.
- **Guideline 2 – Regular Security Testing for Critical Infrastructures and Business Critical Assets – Inventory of Partners and Suppliers:** To cope with the evolving and complex nature of emerging technologies, banks and other financial organizations are advised to perform regular security testing. For instance, regular pentesting processes for key cyber-assets must be performed. In addition to internal testing processes, large financial organizations must establish agreements with trusted security partners in order to regularly stress test their critical infrastructures from a cybersecurity and physical security standpoint. Moreover, banks and financial organizations must maintain a catalogue of technology vendors and partners that could help them keep track of their security issues. This seems imperative in the scope of a complex technological environments, which obliges banks to deal with multiple technology suppliers. For instance, the emergence of LLMs is leading banks to collaborate with new AI vendors (e.g., LLM experts/vendors), which is likely to increase their attack surface unless they have in place disciplined mechanism to track suppliers and partners.
- **Guideline 3 – Security Automation through AI:** Financial organizations must benefit from the increased automation and intelligence of novel technologies (e.g., AI) for cyber-physical security use cases. Various EU projects (including H2020 FINSEC) have already demonstrated the automation potential of AI for security in the financial sector. Nevertheless, this potential is not fully exploited by financial organizations, while novel forms of AI (e.g., federated machine learning, generative AI simulation) have not been explored yet.
- **Guideline 4 – Early Detection:** Despite rising investments into preventive measures, it is still not possible to avoid cyber-attacks. Considering this fact, financial organizations must also invest

on in early detection and preparedness solutions that would minimize the incurred damage and losses in cases where cyber-attacks are successfully launched.

- **Guideline 5 – Security Integration and Zero Trust Architectures (ZTA):** To alleviate the fragmentation of security measures, banks invest in integrated solutions that foster the interplay between different and sometime heterogeneous security solutions for various vendors. Likewise, the establishment of ZTAs will help financial organizations to protect key assets from third-parties access, internal security threats, and poor security measures. ZTA can also help coping with the technological complexity, which often opens new security holes and vulnerabilities. ZTA measures must be considered and implemented in a multi-cloud environment in conjunction with the application of a least privilege access approach.
- **Guideline 6 – Blockchain Security Solutions:** Financial organizations that deal with crypto assets and blockchain based services must partner with organizations and security vendors that specialized in blockchain security. To this end, they must first acknowledge that decentralized blockchain infrastructures and crypto assets are radically different than other types of cyber-assets and required their own specialized security approaches. This is particularly important for financial organizations that establish and manage their own infrastructure. On the other hand, if a financial enterprise relies in a third-party blockchain it should look out for security information and audits of the third-party infrastructure.
- **Guideline 7 – Managed Security Solutions and Security as a Service:** Managed security solutions are a cost-effective alternative for fintechs and smaller enterprises that typically lack the equity capital and knowhow needed to properly invest in cybersecurity. They can also contribute to addressing their employees' poor cybersecurity knowledge, as most of the security functions will be outsourced. In this context, such solutions must be also explored by larger organizations in the scope of a model where part of the security solutions are in-house and others are outsourced to a provider.

3.2. Regulatory Support Guidelines

- **Guideline 8 – Regular Compliance Audits and Continuous Compliance:** To cope with the rapidly evolving regulatory landscape and to ensure compliance at all times, financial organizations are advised to adopt a continuous compliance culture. In this direction, they shall conduct regular audits for regulatory compliance based on partnerships with appropriate experts and auditors.
- **Guideline 9 – CER Adoption and Implementation:** Adherence to the CER directive can help banks and other financial institutions to intensify their risk assessment and compliance processes. To this end, they must adopt risk assessment and infrastructure resilience techniques. CER compliance provides a proper resilience framework that can help financial sector actors to implement some of the other guidelines as well.

3.3. Training, Reskilling and Upskilling Guidelines

- **Guideline 10 – Upskilling and Reskilling Programs:** Financial sector enterprises must invest in upskilling and reskilling programs for their personnel. These programs must be driven by the evolution of the technological and regulatory landscape in the sector and they should aim at educating professionals to contribute to their organization's security and resilience plans.
- **Guideline 11 – Security Awareness Programs:** To address the poor cybersecurity knowledge of banking employees and their customers, banks and financial organizations must enrich existing security awareness programs to address the evolution in technology, processes, regulations, and

security threats. If needed, new security awareness programs should be designed and implemented as well. Consumer awareness programs must focus on retail services and the new security risks (e.g., data theft, identify theft) that come along with new technology like mobile apps, AI chatbots and data-driven decision making.

3.4. Collaboration Guideline

- Guideline 12 – International Collaboration:** Financial sector stakeholders must intensify their collaboration in order to cope with the rising scale of threats and the increasingly interconnected nature of the infrastructures of the sector. The collaboration shall target the development and piloting of supply chain resilience solutions, as well as the specification of common standards and agreed regulations.

Figure 1: Classification of Guidelines for Increased/Improved CIP for Financial Organizations

4. EU-CIP Recommendations for R&I Activities and Roadmaps

The implementation of solutions in-line with the above-listed guidelines is essential for strengthening the resilience of financial infrastructure in ways that address the emerging technological, geopolitical, security and regulatory challenges. R&I activities play a significant role in the design, implementation, and validation of relevant solutions, as they provide opportunities for testing, experimentation, and validation. EU-CIP recommends the following measures that could foster the implementation of the above-listed guidelines.

Recommendation 1 – Specification and grading of CIP/CIR Maturity Levels:

Organizations in the finance sector should assess their CIP maturity considering the sophistication, the automation and completeness of their technological solutions and related CIP policies. A classification into five maturity levels (“Excellent”, “Very Good”, “Good”, “Fair”, “Poor”) can be employed. The “Excellent” level indicates advanced CIP maturity addressing the earlier outlined challenges (C1-C8) and implementing most of the given guidelines (G1-G12). On the other hand, “Poor” maturity indicates that most of the challenges and the solution guidelines remain unaddressed.

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Overall, an organization's level of CIP maturity will determine the type and the density of R&I activities that the organization will have to employ.

Recommendation 2 – Matching Maturity Levels to R&I Roadmap: Financial organizations shall specify their R&I activities roadmap in-line with their maturity levels. The roadmap shall include activities addressed the above-listed guidelines (G1-G12). Organizations with poor CIP maturity and R&D density shall focus on the implementation on most of the outlined activities. Likewise, organizations with “Excellent” maturity shall emphasize the improvement and advance of existing measures.

Recommendation 3 – Clustering of Activities and Implementation Guidelines: The roadmaps must include research, technological development, regulatory auditing, and validation, as well as training and reskilling activities. In this direction, the roadmap shall include activities and support for all the different types of guidelines that were presented earlier. In terms of technological guidelines, solutions for Identity and Access Management (IAM), risk-based access control, multi-factor authentication, Security Information and Event Management (SIEM), Consent Management, Zero Trust Architecture and many more can be employed to support cyber-security functionalities like detection and response, cloud security, risk assessment and mitigation. In terms of regulatory support, measures for developing and validating CER compliance must be employed. In terms of training and upskilling, programs for both financial organizations and their customers must be designed and implemented.

Recommendation 4 – Foster Collaboration Activities at National and EU Scale: In-line with guideline G12, the R&I roadmaps of financial organizations must make provisions for collaborative activities at national and EU scale. This is key to reduce fragmentations and increase the capacity of the various institutions. Collaboration-related activities must strive to reduce costs by streamlining activities (including sharing of information), while at the same time consolidating best practices and lessons learnt. By sharing and coordination of resources more efficiency in the financial supply chain can be achieved.

Recommendation 5 – Develop a Monitoring and Impact Assessment Framework: Financial institutions (including regulators) shall develop a framework for monitoring and assessing the impact of their roadmap, including for example metrics for assessing improvements in preparedness, timeliness, minimization of risks, cost reduction, effectiveness in regulatory compliance, reduction on business interruptions, increasing in consumer awareness, increase in consumer trust, speed for adaptation to the changing threat and regulatory landscape, as well as metrics for assessing the impact of the R&I roadmaps.

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Figure 2: R&I RoadMap Development and Implementation Activities for Financial Organization with a 2030 Outlook

The role of the EU-CIP project

EU-CIP includes coordination and support activities that boost the implementation of the above-listed guidelines and roadmaps. Specifically:

- EU-CIP analyses the state of the art and the state of market to allow the identification of capability gaps and solutions that can help filling in these gaps. The present whitepaper falls in the scope of this analysis. Nevertheless, the project is also identifying and documented sector agnostic capability gaps that can be part of financial institutions R&I roadmaps.
- EU-CIP has documented relevant EU funded projects in CIP, along with other related research and scientific activities. This information is valuable backgrounds for the design of R&I roadmaps for financial organizations.
- EU-CIP has developed a range of innovation support services that can boost the development, deployment, operation, and commercialization of innovative CIP solutions for the financial sector. These services foster the transfer of technological solutions that adhere to the presented guidelines from the realm of research validation to scalable enterprise deployment.
- EU-CIP is developing and providing a range of training and upskilling services (e.g., a training catalogue, a series of CIP-related courses, a map of CIP-related skills profiles to learning paths) that can help financial sector professionals and consumers to improve their CIP skills.
- EU-CIP is supporting the development and build-up of the European CIP ecosystem, which provides opportunities for partnerships and collaborations across different organizations of the financial value chain.

Overall, EU-CIP fosters the development of CIP capabilities that will enable financial organizations to develop the technological capabilities, human capital, organizational processes, and collaborations required to address emerging CIP challenges with a 2030 outlook.

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